

RATE DEPENDENT MULTISCALE MODELLING OF A FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

A new multi-scale modelling technique is used to predict the rate dependent properties of a fibre-reinforced composite. Matrix thermomechanical and stress-strain properties are predicted using Group Interaction Modelling and fibre failure properties are calculated using Finite Element Modelling. Finally, composite strength as a function strain rate is predicted using a statistical model.

Keywords: Multi-scale Modelling, Group Interaction Modelling, Finite Element Model, Statistical Model, Composite Failure Prediction

INTRODUCTION

Multifunctional epoxy resins are frequently used as the matrix in carbon fibre reinforced composites of interest to aerospace and other key industries. The resins display a series of desirable properties such as excellent strength and toughness while maintaining good thermal and electrical characteristics and chemical and environmental resistance. Commercial resin systems are often based on a blend of more than one such epoxy along with an amine curing agent and other additives such as a thermoplastic modifier. The epoxy resins and amine curing agent used in this work are tetraglycidyl 4,4' diaminodiphenylmethane (TGDDM, sold as MY721), triglycidyl *p*-aminophenol (TGAP, sold as MY0510) and diaminodiphenylsulphone (DDS). The chemical structures for these systems are shown in Figure 1 where it can be seen that TGDDM and DDS are tetrafunctional while TGAP is trifunctional. The curing mechanism between epoxy resins and amines is well known [1] and starts with a reaction between an epoxide ring and a primary amine. This is followed by a less favoured reaction between an epoxide ring and a secondary amine. Finally, both reactions create a hydroxide group which can react with an epoxide to create an ether linkage though this reaction is the least likely to occur.

The multifunctional nature of all the reactants in the system leads to a highly crosslinked resin. Despite knowing the curing mechanism, the exact structural details of the 3D network are difficult to predict so a modelling technique that does not require this information will be advantageous [2]. Group Interaction Modelling (GIM) negates the need for exact structural details by treating the polymer in terms of its characteristic mer unit. The technique has been applied extensively to linear polymers [3] and has recently been extended to highly crosslinking thermosetting systems such as those used

in this work [4,5,6]. The first part of the multiscale modelling of a typical aerospace composite consists of using GIM to calculate the thermomechanical and engineering properties of two amine-cured epoxy resins. The predicted strain rate dependent stress-strain curves and moduli of the matrices are then used as input to the fibre fracture model.

Historically, the statistical prediction of fibre failure processes in a composite system has met with mixed results. The standard method is to link a series of single fibre elements of a given ineffective length (IL) in a Monte Carlo simulation, however neglecting the nonlinear behaviour of the matrix has led to inconsistent results. Interfacial shear yielding caused by the viscoelastic nature of an epoxy resin based matrix reduces the probability that a crack will propagate by reducing the strain concentration factor (SCF) felt in fibres adjacent to a fracture [7]. Previous statistical models for the prediction of fibre failure in unidirectional (UD) composites represent the upper and lower bounds [8]. Rosen [9] used the equal load sharing rule between fibres while Zweben [10] used SCF values predicted by Hedgepeth and Van Dyke [11] and their models predicted respectively higher and lower composite failure strengths than seen experimentally. Recent work has shown [12] that an extension to the model proposed by Curtis [13] to account for the yielding nature of the matrix leads to strength predictions in line with experiment. This work attempts to predict strain rate dependent composite strength using the Curtis model and GIM predicted matrix properties.

Figure 1. Chemical structures for TGDDM, TGAP and DDS.

GROUP INTERACTION MODELLING

Method

The prediction of polymer properties using Group Interaction Modelling is an increasingly popular technique [3]. The geometry of the model is a simple hexagonal arrangement of polymer chains with an interchain distance, r . The volume, V , of the polymer scales with r in the two axes normal to the chain, hence V is proportional to r^2 . Each polymer is considered to be a strong 1D oscillator surrounded by a weak 3D field caused by van der Waal's interactions from the six neighbouring chains. The total energy of the system, E_{total} , is defined using a modified Lennard-Jones potential (equation 1) where the relationship between V and r has been taken into account.

$$E_{total} = E_{coh} \left(\left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right)^6 - 2 \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right)^3 \right) \quad (1)$$

The total energy can also be defined in thermodynamic terms (equation 2) where a balance exists between the attractive cohesive energy, E_{coh} , and the repulsive thermal energy, H_T . This expression is for an amorphous isotropic polymer at equilibrium where other thermodynamic contributions can be estimated in terms of E_{coh} . Equations 1 and 2 can be combined to create a series of linked constitutive equations for the prediction of properties as a function of temperature.

$$E_{total} = 0.89 E_{coh} - H_T \quad (2)$$

Each polymer is defined by its mer unit, the smallest subdivision of the chain that still retains its unique characteristics. The mer units for each component of the matrix are characterised in terms of their constituent functional groups, the properties of which are obtained from group contribution tables [3,14]. The parameters required for GIM are the degrees of freedom, N , the cohesive energy at absolute zero, $E_{coh}(0K)$, the van der Waal's volume, V_w , the length, L , and the molecular weight, M .

In viscoelastic polymers, a number of secondary transitions occur in the loss history due to irreversible energy loss via molecular rearrangement. The well known glass transition is caused by a marked increase in intermolecular motion via translation and rotation between polymer chains. The glass transition peak in a typical $\tan\delta$ plot for a highly crosslinking polymer is sharp and occurs at a relatively high temperature ($T_g \approx 250-300$ °C).

In contrast, the beta transition is a much lower temperature peak ($T_b \approx -150-50$ °C) caused by intramolecular motion within the polymer chain. In the TGDDM and TGAP cured with DDS, the beta transition is believed to be caused by the cooperative motion of two 'adjacent but one' phenyl rings. The rotation of the phenyl rings sets up a crankshaft style motion which causes energy loss over a large temperature range (≈ 200 °C). Both transitions are rate dependent and their definition within the model is the method used to incorporate strain rate dependence into GIM. While the glass transition is already well defined in GIM [3], the model for the beta transition is presented here. The beta transition temperature T_b is defined using an Arrhenius expression (equation 3) in terms of the phenyl ring rotation energy, ΔH_b . Also, r is the strain rate, f is the characteristic vibrational frequency of the polymer chain and R is the gas constant. The value of f is obtained from $k\theta_l = hf$ where k and h are the Boltzmann and Planck constants respectively and θ_l is the Debye temperature parallel to the polymer chain.

$$T_b = \frac{-\Delta H_b}{R \ln \left(\frac{r}{2\pi f} \right)} \quad (3)$$

The total loss that occurs through the beta transition, $\tan\Delta_b$, can be obtained using the ratio of elastic energy stored to plastic energy lost through the event. This can be expressed as the ratio of the energy required to perform the beta transition to the energy evolved as heat during it (equation 4). DN and DT represent the change in degrees of

freedom and temperature through the transition respectively. The two transitions are modelled using a normal distribution function.

$$\tan \Delta_b = \frac{R \Delta N T_b}{R N \Delta T} \quad (4)$$

The prediction of properties in GIM is achieved via a series of linked constitutive equations beginning with the thermodynamic energy terms in equation 2. The heat capacity at constant pressure, C_p , is predicted using the Debye model and then integrated with respect to temperature to give H_T . The change in E_{coh} as a function of temperature is dominated by the glass transition where a 50% loss is assumed. The volumetric thermal expansion coefficient, a_v , is predicted from the heat capacity and cohesive energy (equation 5) and can be integrated over temperature using V_w , to give V .

$$a_v = \frac{1.38 C_p}{R E_{coh}} \quad (5)$$

Using equation 2, H_T and E_{coh} combine to give the total energy, E_{total} . The elastic bulk modulus, B_e , is predicted as an energy density term (equation 6) combining the total energy and volume.

$$B_e = 18 \frac{E_{total}}{V} \quad (6)$$

The known relationship [15] between the total cumulative loss tangent, $\tan \Delta$, and the temperature gradient of the Young's modulus, E , can be expressed via a proportionality constant, A . This leads to an expression for E in terms of the elastic bulk modulus and the loss tangent (equation 7).

$$E = B_e \exp\left(\frac{-\tan \Delta}{A B_e}\right) \quad \text{where} \quad A = \frac{15 L}{\theta_1 M} \quad (7)$$

For the purposes of the model, the definition of strain is divided into an elastic and inelastic contribution. An expression for the elastic strain, e_e , is obtained by integrating the expansion coefficient over temperature to give a dimension change equivalent to the strain (equation 8). The loss tangent is then applied to give the total strain, e .

$$e_e = \int_0^T a_l dT \quad \& \quad e = e_e \left(1 + \int_0^T \tan d dT\right) \quad (8)$$

The Young modulus and strain values are combined to give a value of stress complete with a correction for converting from tension to compression equal to twice the Poisson's ratio, n .

$$s_c = \frac{E e}{2n} \quad (9)$$

Results

Stoichiometrically, TGDDM and DDS combine in a ratio of 1:1 as they are both tetrafunctional. TGAP and DDS combine in a ratio of 4:3 as the former is trifunctional. Whilst this leads to TGDDM/DDS being a relatively simple combination of the epoxy and amine, another complicating factor exists in TGAP/DDS. The third reaction mentioned in the mechanism (see introduction) is more likely to occur in TGAP than in TGDDM. The reason for this is probably due to mobility constraints in TGDDM. When TGDDM is partially reacted (i.e. 3 of 4 sites attached) it is significantly less mobile than a similarly reacted TGAP (i.e. 2 of 3 sites attached). The pinning down of TGDDM via three points fixes it in place whereas TGAP is only pinned by two points and hence still able to rotate to meet an incoming reactant.

GIM parameter values used in the matrix property prediction are shown in Table 1. Each functional group makes a fixed parameter contribution to each mer unit type (E-OH represents the product of the hydroxide-epoxy reaction). The cured mer unit parameters values are obtained using the component ratios in the previous paragraph. Both TGDDM/DDS and TGAP/DDS are highly crosslinked systems and the final value of N is reduced by 3 for each crosslinking site.

Table 1. GIM parameters for functional groups, mer units and cured mer units.

Group	N	$E_{coh}(0K)$ (J/mol)	V_w (cm ³ /mol)
CH ₂	2	4500	10.25
Phenyl	3	25000	43.3
N	2	9000	4
Epoxy	4	15300	22
CH(OH)	2	20800	11.5
SO ₂	2	45000	20.3
TGDDM Mer Unit	36	191700	232.9
TGAP Mer Unit	25	129700	148.3
DDS Mer Unit	12	113000	114.9
E-OH Mer Unit	22	119700	148.3
Cured TGDDM/DDS	24	152350	173.9
Cured TGAP/DDS	19	121116	134.0

When the model is run for TGDDM/DDS and TGAP/DDS a series of linked properties are predicted as a function of temperature from absolute zero to beyond the glass transition [16]. The volumetric coefficient of thermal expansion and Young's modulus for both resins are shown in Figure 2 and vary as expected. There are clear changes around the beta transition temperature (~ -50 °C) and the glass transition temperature (~ 275 °C) which compare very well with experimental data [17].

Figure 2. GIM predicted volumetric coefficient of thermal expansion and Young's modulus for TGDDM/DDS (l) and TGAP/DDS (r) at room temperature and 0.00167/s.

The GIM predicted compressive stress-strain curves for both resins are shown in Figure 3 along with the experimental equivalents where excellent agreement is observed. The yield condition is predicted almost exactly in both the stress and strain axes and there are only small discrepancies post-yield due to strain-hardening and softening. The latter isn't included in the GIM predictions currently and won't affect the composite modelling that follows.

Figure 3. GIM predicted and experimental compressive stress-strain curves for TGDDM/DDS (l) and TGAP/DDS (r) at room temperature and 0.00167/s.

The variation of the predicted Young's modulus and yield stress with strain rate compared to experimental values is shown in Figure 4 for both resins. The agreement between GIM predicted and experimental values for both the modulus and yield stress over three different strain rates and two different resins is excellent. There is very little discrepancy between the two and the predicted values are well within the accepted 5% error associated with experiments of this type.

Figure 4. GIM predicted and experimental Young's modulus and yield stress as a function of strain rate for TGDDM/DDS (l) and TGAP/DDS (r) at room temperature.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Method

The second part of the multiscale modelling of a composite system is to assess the effect a broken fibre has on neighbouring fibres when the surrounding matrix is either TGDDM/DDS or TGAP/DDS. To do this a composite system was assembled using a finite element code (Ansys 11) so that the consequences of a fibre break could be simulated. A 1/12th slice of a hexagonal UD composite of length 100 μm was created with a fibre volume fraction of 50%. The materials were set up with the SOLID45 element such that the fibres were orthotropic and the matrix was isotropic. The longitudinal and transverse properties of the fibre were taken from a study of HTA3151 carbon fibre [18] and the GIM predicted multilinear stress-strain curves and moduli were used for the matrix.

The unit cell of elements is shown in Figure 5 where the magnified section shows the top layer of elements of the central fibre has been removed to simulate a break. When a 1% tensile strain is applied to the top surface in the z-direction, the central fibre is left behind and the neighbouring fibres experience a strain concentration via the matrix. The model assumes perfect interfacial bonding between the matrix and fibre and that failure occurs via fibres breaking and not matrix cracking. The IL is defined as the length of the broken fibre required to return to 90% of the applied strain and the SCF is the ratio of the mean axial strain across a cross section of the neighbouring fibre to the applied strain.

Figure 5. The hexagonal unit cell of elements used for simulating a single fibre break.

Results

The axial strain experienced by the hexagonal unit cell is shown in Figure 6. The central fibre is broken while the surrounding fibres have moved in the z-direction and hence show enhanced strain values, especially in the vicinity of the break point. The strain observed in next-nearest neighbours is observed to be $\approx 1\%$ across the whole fibre length and therefore only the nearest neighbours are considered in the following analysis. When a double break occurs, several of the neighbouring fibres will experience an even greater strain concentration and this is modelled using a rectangular unit cell as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Contour plots of the axial strain for a single and double fibre breaks in a UD composite. The matrix (TGDDM/DDS) is not shown for clarity.

The values of IL and SCF as a function of the strain rate dependent matrix properties are shown in Table 2. For both TGDDM and TGAP, an increase in strain rate reduces the IL and increases the SCF. This is consistent with the viscoelastic nature of the matrix where increasing the rate inhibits the molecular rearrangement processes discussed earlier from happening. When perturbed at a higher rate, any relaxation is allowed less time to occur, reducing the length over which the effects of a fibre breakage occur, correspondingly reducing IL and increasing SCF.

Table 2. Ineffective lengths and strain concentration factors as a function of rate.

Matrix	Strain Rate (/s)	IL (mm)	SCF (single break)
TGDDM/DDS	0.000167	0.165	1.102
	0.00167	0.161	1.103
	0.0167	0.154	1.104
TGAP/DDS	0.000167	0.176	1.090
	0.00167	0.162	1.091
	0.0167	0.147	1.092

STATISTICAL MODELLING

Method

The effect a fibre breakage has on its neighbours is now extended to predict how fibre failure propagates through a composite system. A single composite layer of thickness equal to the IL and consisting of a 20x20 array of fibres was assigned random failure strains using the Box-Muller method [19]. The Priest-Bader method was used to assign a mean failure strain based on the IL and also to extrapolate to longer composite lengths [20]. The model assumes that no delamination occurs between layers and uses the weakest link approach where the minimum failure strain is located and this fibre is assumed to break first. The six nearest neighbouring fibres to the break have their current strain intensified using the SCF for a single break and these values are compared to their failure strains. Should a further break occur, the process is repeated using the SCF for a double break. The current strain is then increased to the next lowest failure strain which causes the next break. The process is repeated until the criteria for an unstable crack are achieved, which in this work is either 2% or 3 adjacent fibres broken. At this stage, the layer failure strain is the current strain and the process is repeated for ~50 iterations until self-consistency is seen.

The average failure strain of a composite of N layers, $\bar{e}_{composite}$, can be obtained using equation 10 where \bar{e}_{lf} is the average failure strain of the layers, z_l is the probability of layer failure obtained from standard tables and S_l is the standard deviation of failure strain in the layers.

$$\bar{e}_{composite} = \bar{e}_{lf} - z_l S_l \quad (10)$$

Results

Running the model on a composite consisting of N layers of HTA5131 carbon fibres surrounded by TGDDM/DDS matrix results in values of failure strain against length as shown in Figure 7. As the length of the composite is increased, the failure strain

decreases and eventually achieves a minimum value. In a similar standard system this value is close to experimental measurements [12]. As the strain rate is increased, the failure strain of the composite decreases which ties in with the changes observed in the IL and SCF. The increasing rate reduces the ability of the polymer to dissipate energy through molecular rearrangements and hence the composite fails at a correspondingly lower strain.

Figure 7. The variation of composite failure strain with length as a function of strain rate. The matrix is TGDDM/DDS.

CONCLUSIONS

A multiscale modelling technique has been presented which is capable of predicting rate dependent composite failure properties from fundamental inputs. Group Interaction Modelling predicts non-linear polymer matrix properties from basic parameters such as the chemical structure as a function of temperature, strain and strain rate. The data is used to predict the effect a fibre break has on surrounding fibres in a typical composite system. This is then used to predict the statistical propagation of fibre failure events through a composite of varying length. The rate dependent failure properties of the composite are linked to the viscoelastic nature of the polymeric matrix.

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